

PERSONALITY RESEARCH METHODS**Tursunboyeva Guljahon Qurolboy qizi**

Student at Karakalpak State University

Mangliyeva Nozima Olloyor qizi

Student at Karakalpak State University

Kamalova Sevara Yuldashevna

Student at Karakalpak State University

Tuvaqov Asadbek Jumaboy o'g'li

Student at Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15513263>

Abstract. This study examines the concepts of projection and self-projection, the characteristics and classification of projective techniques. It provides a description of the goals and stages of the "Associative Drawing Test" technique, aimed at identifying and actively using the potential of the individual.

Keywords: personality psychology, character, psychological processes, philosophical and literary period, clinical period, purely experimental period, projective method, test, intelligence, hypothesis, associative method, experiment, interpretation.

SHAXSNI TADQIQ ETISH METODLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot loyihalar va avtolojihalar tushunchalarini, proektiv usullarni tan olish va tasniflashni o'rganadi. Xususiyatlari berilgan, "Shaxsning potentsialini aniqlash va faol foydalanishga qaratilgan assotsiativ chizma testi" usulining maqsadlari va bosqichlari tavsiflangan.

Kalit so'zlar: shaxs psixologiyasi, xarakter, psixologik jarayonlar, falsafiy va adabiy davr, klinik davr, sof eksperimental davr, proyektiv usul, test, intellekt, gipoteza, assotsiativ metod, eksperiment, talqin.

МЕТОДЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматриваются понятия проекции и самопроекции, признаки и классификация проективных методик. Дается характеристика, описываются цели и этапы методики «Тест ассоциативного рисования, ориентированной на выявление и активное использование потенциала личности.

Ключевые слова: психология личности, характер, психологические процессы, философско-литературный период, клинический период, чисто экспериментальный

период, проективный метод, тест, интеллект, гипотеза, ассоциативный метод, эксперимент, интерпретация.

Introduction

The category of "personality" is the most important, basic concept of general psychology, while the section "personality psychology" forms its basis. Knowledge of this area of psychology allows any specialist to work effectively.

To characterize a person as a subject of activity, it is necessary and sufficient to characterize his attitude to the activity. Since human consciousness is generally active, relationships are not only the mental properties of the individual, but also the qualitative features of mental processes: observation, sensitivity, attentiveness. Motives of activity can also be characterized as relationships: needs and interests. Therefore, the general principles of psychological research of personality are determined by how the relationships of the individual are understood. Personality psychology became an experimental science in the first decade of the 20th century. However, theoretical research began much earlier. In the history of personality studies, three main periods can be distinguished:

- Philosophical-literary period;
- Clinical period;
- Purely experimental period.

Philosophical-literary period. This period began in antiquity and lasted until the beginning of the 19th century. During this period, information related to personality psychology was mainly reflected in the works of philosophers and writers, in which the moral and social nature of the individual was discussed. The definition of the individual in the philosophical-literary period was very comprehensive, covering the biology, psychology, behavior, culture, and even property of the individual. Methodology of psychological research is a set of methods used in a specific study and determined by the corresponding methodology. Methods of personality research include testing and projective techniques. Projective method is a method of personality research based on identifying projections of the personality traits of the subject in the experimental data with subsequent interpretation.

Test (from the English test - sample, trial) is a standardized task, the result of which allows measuring the psychological characteristics of the subject. Thus, the purpose of a test study is to test, diagnose certain psychological characteristics of a person, and its result is a quantitative indicator that is correlated with previously established relevant norms and

standards. The use of certain and specific tests in psychology most clearly demonstrates the general theoretical principles of the researcher and the entire study. Thus, in foreign psychology, test studies are usually understood as a means of identifying and measuring the innate intellectual and characterological characteristics of subjects.

Tests are distinguished: ability and achievement tests, as well as personality tests (questionnaires, projective). Ability tests are designed to measure the level of development of certain abilities (mental processes, intelligence, professional abilities) in an individual.

Achievement tests are used to determine achievements in various types of activities (study, work). Personality tests are designed to determine various psychological qualities of an individual (motives, relationships, values), individual characteristics (temperament, character, emotional state). Questionnaires or projective tests are used for this. Validity is the correspondence of test results to the characteristic it is intended to measure. Reliability is the property of a test to give similar results upon repeated measurement. Reliability as internal consistency is the focus of all elements of a test scale on measuring one quality.

Representativeness is the correspondence between the norms (intervals on a test scale) obtained on a sample and the norms that can be obtained on a population. Reliability is the property of a test to counteract falsification - intentional or unconscious distortion of results by subjects. The main feature of projective techniques can be designated as a relatively unstructured task, i.e. a task that allows for an almost unlimited variety of possible answers. In order for the individual's imagination to run wild, only brief, general instructions are given. For the same reason, test stimuli are usually vague or ambiguous. The hypothesis on which such tasks are built is that the way an individual perceives and interprets test material or "structures" of a situation should reflect fundamental aspects of the functioning of his psyche. Usually, projective techniques are also methods of disguised testing, since the subject rarely suspects the type of psychological interpretation that will be given to his answers. The projective method is provided by a set of projective techniques (projective tests), among which are: a) associative (for example, the Rorschach test, the test of unfinished sentences); b) interpretative (for example, the thematic apperception test (TAT), which requires interpreting social situations depicted in pictures); c) expressive (e.g. psychodrama, drawing of a person, non-existent animal).

Associative experiment is one of the first projective methods. Z. Freud and his followers assumed that uncontrolled associations are a symbolic or sometimes even direct projection of the internal, often unconscious content of consciousness.

This allows using an associative experiment to identify and describe affective complexes. In the context of such an understanding of associations, all projective techniques can be classified as a type of associative experiment.

Conversation method - the specific role of conversation as a method of personality research follows from the fact that in it the subject gives a verbal report on the properties and manifestations of his personality. Therefore, in a conversation, the subjective side of the personality is revealed with the greatest completeness - self-awareness and self-assessment of personality properties, experiences and emotional attitude expressed in them, etc.

The correct formulation of questions is of great importance. A necessary condition for this method is the presence of a trusting contact between the subject and the experimenter.

The method of characterological conversation is a special form of natural experiment.

A special place in the system of research methods, intermediate between the observation method and artificial experiment, is occupied by the "natural experiment" of A.F. Lazursky. A characteristic feature of a natural experiment is that it brings the study closer to natural conditions; it is carried out in a normal environment for the subject. Using the method of a natural experiment, it is possible to observe the subject under certain conditions in purposefully created situations, organizing observation according to a pre-planned plan. Observation of the behavior and reactions of the subject allows you to get an idea of the characteristics of the personality as a whole and its individual properties.

Biographical method - allows you to study the stages of the life path, the features of personality formation, can be a supplement when interpreting data obtained by experimental methods. Questionnaires as one of the methods for studying personality are used to diagnose the degree of expression of certain personal characterological or other traits in an individual.

There are 2 types of questionnaires:

- one-dimensional - one particular characteristic is diagnosed
- multidimensional - provide information about a whole range of different personality traits. Only closed questions.

Questionnaires consist of a number of scales or factors. Each scale includes a set of questions, statements aimed at identifying a particular property. The emergence of a projective approach to personality diagnostics is an important stage in the development of psychodiagnostics, as methods appear that are qualitatively different from traditional ones.

Projective methods are widely used in the practice of personality research in all areas of modern psychology.

It is known that people's drawings reveal significant features of their personality, their deepest personal problems. Drawing in psychology is a kind of self-projection of the personality, a creative process. At the moment of drawing, a person uses the entire system of his psychological capabilities (conscious, unconscious). Let us consider in more detail the concept of projection. The psychological concept of projection (from the Latin *projectio* - throwing out, throwing forward) first appears in psychoanalysis, belongs to Z. Freud (1894) and is associated with the defense mechanisms of the "I". Understanding projection as a defense mechanism was called "classical projection". Subsequently, both within and outside psychoanalysis, the concept of projection received different interpretations. Projective techniques were first considered in the studies of F. Galton, who studied the associative process. Later, K. G. Jung created a test that allowed one to actualize experiences - personality complexes. In the late 19th - early 20th centuries, F. E. Rybakov actively explored imagination. At the same time, A. Binet in France experimented with amorphous colored and monochrome ink spots. All these studies are considered the prehistory of the projective technique.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the effective use of a method depends on its validity and reliability. Reliability and validity are the criteria by which the quality and high efficiency of psychological diagnosis can be determined.

Used literature

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
2. Kurbanova, R. J., and B. E. Saidboeva. "MAKTAB VA OILADA ESTETIK TARBIYANI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING AKSILOGIK DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Inter education & global study* 9 (2024): 114-121.
3. Jarasovna, Kurbanova Rita. "The Role of National Values in Shaping the Aesthetic Worldview of Schoolchildren." *International Journal of Pedagogics* 5.03 (2025): 55-58.
4. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "USE OF PEDAGOGICAL METHODS BASED ON THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION." *European International Journal of Pedagogics* 4.06 (2024): 26-33.

5. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "Program Technology for Choosing an Effective Educational Methodology Based on Modern Pedagogical Research in The Educational System." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS* 6.02 (2025): 30-33.
6. Turemuratova, Aziza, Shahlo Matmuratova, and Nargisa Tajieva. "THE DEPENDENCE OF MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES ON PEDAGOGICAL METHODS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN IMPROVING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 50-55.
7. Aziza, Turemuratova. "KONFLIKT VA UNING KELIB CHIQISH SABABLARI." *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке* 3.32 (2025): 457-459.
8. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza. "PSYCHOLOGICAL CONFIDENTIALITY OF THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES IN EDUCATION." (2025).
9. Turemuratova, Aziza, Azamat Utambetov, and Rinat Seytimov. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENING ASOSLARI TUSHUNCHASI VA O'SMIRLARNING KOLLOBORATIV KO'NIKMALARINI OSHIRUVCHI PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLAR." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 135-141.
10. Turemuratova, Aziza, Farog'at Seytmambetova, and Nazokat Masharipova. "PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNING USLUBIY MUMMOLARI VA KOLLOBORATIV TA'LIMDA GURUH MUAMMOLARI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 100-106.
11. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza, and Turganbayeva Amina Quanishbayevna. "PSIXOLOG TRENERNING KASBIY KO'NIKMALARI VA PSIXOLOGIK SALOHİYATINI OSHIRUVCHI AMALIY TRENINGLAR." (2025).
12. Turemuratova, Aziza, Aynisa Jaqsimuratova, and Ramiza Mustapaeva. "SELF-CONTROL RULES OF A PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINER." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 217-221.
13. Muratbayevna, Dauletova Gozal, and Madaminova Nargiza Qurbanbayevna. "BOLANING RIVOJLANISH DAVRI PSIXOLOGIYASI." *Scientific Impulse* 1 (2022): 33-35.
14. Reyimbaevna, Mambetiyarova Venera, and Jumabayeva Marupa. "OTA-ONA VA FARZANDLAR MUNOSABATINING XUSUSIYATLARI." *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ* 51 (2024): 20-23.